

ASSESSMENT OF ACADEMIC STRESS COPING STRATEGIES AMONG NURSING STUDENTS IN PRIVATE NURSING INSTITUTES OF KARACHI, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Background:

Nursing students are frequently exposed to academic and clinical stressors due to demanding coursework, clinical responsibilities, and expectations of professional competence. These stressors can negatively impact their psychological well-being and academic performance. Understanding coping strategies is essential for supporting students in managing stress effectively.

Objective

To assess the coping strategies used by nursing students to manage academic stress and to examine their association with selected demographic variables in private nursing institutes of Karachi, Pakistan.

Methods:

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 400 nursing students from four private nursing institutes in Karachi. Participants were selected using convenient purposive sampling. Data were collected using the standardized COPE Inventory questionnaire. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 20, including descriptive statistics and one-way ANOVA to determine associations between coping strategies and demographic variables.

Results:

The majority of participants were female (62.5%) and aged between 21–25 years. Religious coping strategies were the most commonly used (19.15%), followed by optimistic coping (17.62%) and problem-solving strategies (17.36%). Emotional (11.11%) and motivational strategies (7.83%) were less frequently used. Significant differences in coping

strategies were observed across institutes ($p < 0.01$), while no significant association was found with gender ($p = 0.609$).

Conclusion:

Nursing students experience considerable academic stress and utilize a range of coping strategies, with religious coping being the most dominant. Educational institutions should implement structured support systems, including counseling and stress management programs, to promote effective coping and enhance student well-being.

INTRODUCTION

Nursing students are frequently exposed to academic and clinical stressors due to demanding coursework, clinical responsibilities, and expectations of professional competence. These stressors may affect their psychological wellbeing and academic performance. Understanding coping strategies used by nursing students is important for developing supportive educational environments.

Pressure exerted on organic system in terms of organism's unspecific reaction is defined as stress. Coping demands several adaptations from an individual in everyday situations and constant instability imposed by modern era¹. Interaction between the inner and outer environments of individuals occurs as a complex event. A physical, mental, emotional, and behavioral change comes as a result of this mutual interaction. These responses motivate individuals to make use of coping mechanisms, depends on the nature of stressors, generated by the individual's repercussions and its assessment of the event which give direction to organic responses². An ability that allows people to react to behaviors, thoughts and emotions, caused by such events as well as an individual's capacity to face and adapt to stressful situations is defined as coping³. An attempt to control the organism's physical and emotional reactions and manage stressful situations, additionally to incorporates with threatening events as a set of strategies aimed at adaptation by increasing quality of life by reducing stress levels can be defined as coping. It is the Unique and singular, different forms of adaptation and coping, based on personality and each person's life experiences involve personal factors of cultural and emotional order that depends on several elements⁴. Coping can lead to

the overcoming of a problem or reduction of stress when used correctly. On the contrary it may increase stress level when strategies are not appropriate to a given situation⁵. Students start a new phase of their lives that is, they must deal with changes and adapt to this new environment and circumstances on entering University⁶. Nursing students tend to be more exposed to stressful event and this research is all about as nursing students they are responsible for the health and lives of others in which they are almost constantly experiencing stressful situation which results in enormous stress¹. Nursing students experience stress and even abandon their profession as a result of the great demands, requirements, internal and external pressures in terms of their course frequent exposure to human suffering that is why nursing is considered an extremely stressful occupation^{7,8}.

Coping Strategies

It is easy for nursing students to fall into negative patterns of thinking as a result of stress that have a tremendous impact on how nursing students feel at school and at home. There are number of interventions to help to minimize the stress of nursing students⁹. Strategies like cognitive behavioral that help nursing students to feel better and avoid self-defeating thoughts as suggested by studies¹⁰. Coping strategies help nursing students to increase their emotional self-management and leads to change things which they can adjust¹¹.

Problems Which Induce Stress

In conjunction with elevated intrapersonal stressors, the external stressors including increased clinical responsibilities and the course requirements add to increased levels of stress¹². Poor academic performance and because of

suffering from *burnout*—a term used for emotional exhaustion and diminished interest / feelings of exhausted owing to study requirements. Segregated behavior towards study and the perception of oneself as incompetent which is the sign of professional insufficiency, are the manifestations of this phenomenon¹¹.

Problem Statement

Nursing students are exposed to significant levels of academic and clinical stress due to demanding coursework, frequent examinations, clinical responsibilities, and the pressure to develop professional competence. These stressors can adversely affect students' psychological well-being, academic performance, and overall quality of life. If not properly managed, stress may lead to emotional exhaustion, decreased motivation, poor academic outcomes, and even withdrawal from nursing programs.

Although coping strategies play a crucial role in managing stress, not all students utilize effective or adaptive coping mechanisms. Some may rely on negative strategies, which can further aggravate stress and hinder their personal and professional development.

In Pakistan, particularly in private nursing institutes of Karachi, there is limited empirical evidence regarding how nursing students cope with academic stress and how demographic factors such as age and gender influence these coping strategies. This lack of localized data makes it difficult for educators and policymakers to design appropriate interventions and support systems.

Therefore, this study aims to assess the coping strategies used by nursing students to manage academic stress and to explore their association with selected demographic variables, in order to provide evidence-based recommendations for improving student support and educational outcomes.

Aim of the study

The aim of this study is to identify coping strategies for stress, related to academics that are used by nursing students at private nursing institutes in Karachi, Pakistan..

Objectives

- To identify coping strategies for stress used by nursing students in private nursing institutes in Karachi, Pakistan.
- To identify the association between age and gender with effective coping strategies amongst nursing students at private nursing institutes in Karachi Pakistan.

Research Questions

- What are the coping strategies that are used by the nursing students at private nursing institutes in Karachi, Pakistan?
- Is there any association between age and gender with effective coping strategies?

Rationale of the study

Nursing education is widely recognized as academically and clinically demanding, exposing students to multiple stressors such as heavy coursework, clinical responsibilities, examination pressure, and interactions with patients and healthcare professionals. These stressors can significantly affect the psychological wellbeing, academic performance, and professional development of nursing students. Increased levels of stress may lead to emotional exhaustion, decreased concentration, poor academic outcomes, and even withdrawal from nursing programs.

Coping strategies play a critical role in enabling nursing students to manage stress effectively and maintain their academic and emotional stability. Effective coping mechanisms can help students adapt to challenging situations, reduce psychological distress, and enhance their overall performance during nursing education. Conversely, ineffective coping strategies may increase stress levels and negatively impact learning outcomes and professional growth.

Although several international studies have examined stress and coping strategies among nursing students, limited research has been conducted in Pakistan, particularly in private nursing institutes. Cultural, educational, and social factors may influence how students perceive stress and the coping mechanisms they adopt.

Therefore, it is essential to investigate coping strategies within the local context to better understand how nursing students manage academic stress.

Hence, this study was conducted to identify the coping strategies used by nursing students to manage academic-related stress in private nursing institutes in Karachi, Pakistan, and to examine their association with selected demographic variables such as age and gender.

Significance of the study

This study is significant because it contributes to the limited body of knowledge regarding coping strategies among nursing students in Pakistan. Previous literature indicates that most research on this topic has been conducted in Western countries, and there is a scarcity of local studies exploring how Pakistani nursing students manage academic stress.

The findings of this study will help nursing educators, administrators, and policymakers understand the types of coping strategies adopted by nursing students in response to academic stress. This knowledge can assist educational institutions in developing appropriate interventions, support systems, and counseling programs to improve students' psychological wellbeing and academic success.

Operational Definitions

Nursing student

A nursing student is a student in a post-higher secondary educational program that leads to degree and licensing to practice nursing.

Stress

Pressure exerted on organic system in terms of organism's unspecific reaction is defined as stress.

Coping

An ability that allows people to react to behaviors, thoughts and emotions, caused by such events as well as an individual's capacity to face and adapt to stressful situations is defined as coping

Optimistic

Tendency towards favorable or hopeful outcome

Ransference

Redirection of feelings or emotions toward a substitute.

Emotional

Feeling of excitement due to oversensitivity of an individual.

Motivational

Tendency of individual to achieve goal.

Religious

Turning towards spiritual beliefs to solve problems.

Negative

An act of refusing and considering only the dark aspects of things.

Problem Solving

Obsessed with idea of solving concerning issues

Methodology

This chapter represents the methodology that has been applied to identify the coping strategies adopted by the nursing students against the stress. It describes the techniques that have been used to evaluate the sampling, collection of data, study type, place of the study, ethical consideration, inclusion and exclusion criteria. The overall study is the cross-sectional type based on the survey done at one point in time.

Study Design

This study was based on a design of cross sectional in order to assess the coping strategies for stress among nursing students at private institutes. This design was used to determine the outcome of the interest within a population at a given point in time for the population or subgroups⁵⁴. The cross-sectional descriptive design of this study was thought as a relevant study design because usually cross-sectional studies are conducted by means of survey and sample is usually taken from the whole population which can estimate the prevalence of outcome of interest^{55,56}.

Study Setting & Population

It was a cross sectional study completed in Karachi. WHO Calculator named as "Open EPI" has been used for sample size calculation. A previous study done in Jordan, April 2022 "Sources of Stress and Coping Behaviors in Clinical Practice among Baccalaureate Nursing Students" would be considered to calculate sample size. 47.82% nurses had stress levels above the mean level of stress stated in above mentioned study. Considering 95% confidence level and 5% bound of error, sample size is $n = 384$. Data was collected from $N = 400$ nursing students participants were enrolled from in (Institute A, Institute B, Institute C, and Institute D) in Karachi, Pakistan. The institutes were selected as per convenience depending upon the travel time, cooperation available from the institute management and administration. Convenient-purposive sampling method was used to recruit the study participants.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The investigators must specify inclusion and exclusion criteria for participation in the study in any research that helps researcher at optimized research additionally in order to yield better results for researchers. Inclusion and exclusion of participants determine the scope and validity of results that is why selection process is very important. The following inclusion and exclusion criteria were used in current study:

Inclusion Criteria

- Nursing students who were enrolled in Fours years degree program
- Nursing students between the ages of 16-30 were included
- Nursing students of both genders were the part of the study

Exclusion Criteria

- Students below 16 years and above 30 years of age were excluded from the study as per criteria for the enrolment of students in Degree program by Pakistan Nursing Council (PNC).
- Four year students due to unavailability in their parents Institute. These students were on

their practicum area and were not present.

Data Collection Tool

A tool selected for data collection was structured questionnaire for nursing students COPE inventory by Michael Scheier, regarding the coping strategies adopted by nursing students at private nursing institutes in Karachi, Pakistan (refer Appendix A for questionnaire). COPE inventory is declared open to be used for research study to assess coping strategies (refer Appendix B). It has been authorized by the Department of Psychology, College of Arts and Sciences, University of Miami on their official website. COPE inventory includes both functional and non-functional coping resources. The questionnaire has been modified according to the cultural setting. The questionnaire includes total 40 statements that need or needs to be responded responding on likert scale. The likert scale comprised of "I usually don't do this, I usually do this at all, little bit I usually do this and I usually do this medium amount ." The scale range was from 5 - 20. High score represents best coping strategies utilized by nursing students. The students' data collecting tool in English and has been translated into Urdu for better understanding of the students. It has 15 major components that includes Positive reinterpretation and growth, mental disengagement, focus on and venting of emotions, use of instrumental social support, active coping, denial, religious coping, humor, behavioral disengagement, restraint, use of emotional social support, substance use, acceptance, suppression of competing activities, and planning.

Subject Selection

Prior to conducting the study, permission from the respective institution was obtained. The participants were all informed about the purpose of conducting the study. After seeking their consent, they were told to fill a questionnaire. The registered students were the ones who had given their consents for the participation for data collection. Students were properly assisted while they were working in the questionnaire. In total 400 students were enrolled from which 150 were

male and 250 were female nursing students and none of them refused to participate in the study from the either gender.

Data Analysis Process

Data was analyzed with regard to percentage of coping strategies used by nursing student by using SPSS version 20. The analysis was totally descriptive type with respect to age, gender, class and campus. One way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test was applied by making scale by sum of coping score from lower (1) to highest (4) value in terms of coping strategies but factors which have negative impact on strategies, the scale is from higher (4) to lower (1). One way ANOVA test compares the means between the interested groups and determines whether any of those means are statistically significant and different from each other. The data was presented in table form while demographic data were presented in graphical format.

Validity and Reliability of the Tool

Approach that arrests the measurement properties of the questionnaire are the validity and reliability. In scientific method validity and reliability are the fundamental cornerstones. The reliability of COPE inventory ranges from 0.45 to 0.92 for different components. The questionnaire was pilot tested on 10% of the total sample size that is 40 nursing students from unique hospital and institute of nursing however this sample was not included in this study. The aim of the pilot testing was to ensure that the questionnaire was

understood and comprehended clearly and thus overall the validity and reliability was adequate to conduct research.

Ethical Considerations

Confidentiality and privacy was maintained throughout the study. All questionnaires were coded by researcher to maintain anonymity. Raw data was kept in locked cabinet to ensure confidentiality of study participants. The soft copy of data was kept password protected.

Permission was taken from respective organization and informed consent was taken from the participants in order to maintain autonomous decision. Participants were only chosen their participation by their free will.

- No direct benefit or risk was associated with this research.
- Any student who met the inclusion criteria was given equal opportunity to participate in study.

3.0 Results

Socio and Demographic Profile of Participants

Age Group Status

In this study 400 nursing students participated. From the total participants 50% of the participants' age was ranging from 21 to 25 years. Whereas, 39% of the participants were between the ages of 16 to 20 years, lastly only 11% of the participants were having age between 26 to 29 years as shown in figure 4.1.

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document.-1: Determined demographic properties with respect to Age (N =400)

Campus Status

The participants were divided according to the percentages that is 38% of the participants were included from Institute D, 26% of participants were included from Institute A, 19% of the participants were included from Institute B and

last but not least 17% of the participants which is the lowest percentage was obtained from Institute C as shown in figure 4.2. The ratio of the participants was divided according to the availability and agreement to sign the consent form by the students.

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Figure Error! No text of specified style in document.-2: Determined demographic properties with respect to Campus (N=400)

Class Status

Total 400 participants participated, from the total participants, 38% of the participants in this study were from year II of Degree in Nursing Program,

31% of the participants were from year I of Degree in Nursing Program and similarly 31% participants were from year III of Degree in Nursing Program as shown in figure 4.3.

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document.-3: Determined demographic properties with respect to Class (N=400)

Gender Status

From the total participants, 62.5% of the participants were female whereas, 37.5% of the participants were male, shown in figure 4.4.

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document.-4: Determined Demographic Properties with Respect to Gender (N=400)

Staying Optimistic Coping Strategies used by Nursing Students

Table 4.1 show the staying optimistic coping strategies usually used by nursing students. There were total eight statements assessing the optimistic coping strategies. The statement “I learn something from the experience” was marked by 29% of the students. Statement “I force myself to wait for the right time to do something” and “I try to make it seem more positive” found to be 20%,

“I try to grow as a person as a result of the experience” found to be 18%, “I concentrate my efforts on doing something about it” found to be 17%, “I accept that this has happened and that it can't be changed” found to be 14%, “I keep myself from getting distracted by other thoughts or activities” found to be 13%, while the least percentage obtained 10% by the statement “I learn to live with it”.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-1: Showing percentage of staying optimistic coping strategies used by nursing students

S. NO.	Statement	I usually don't do this	I usually do this, little bit	I usually do this in medium amount	I usually do this at all
Staying Optimistic					
1	I try to grow as a person as a result of the experience.	28%	43%	11%	18%
2	I concentrate my efforts on doing something about it.	34%	25%	24%	17%
3	I keep myself from getting distracted by other thoughts or activities.	33%	26%	26%	15%
4	I accept that this has happened and that it can't be changed	14.5%	39.5%	32%	14%
5	I try to make it seem more positive.	20%	37%	23%	20%
6	I force myself to wait for the right time to do something.	19%	36%	25%	20%
7	I learn to live with it.	43.5%	26%	20.5%	10%
8	I learn something from the experience.	19%	22%	30%	29%

Transference Coping Strategies used by Nursing Students

The transference coping strategies assessed by the four statements mentioned in table 4.2. The highest percentage obtained from the statement “I get sympathy and understanding from people” found to be 30% followed by the statement “I

make fun of the situation” found to be 26%, “I day dream about things other than this” found to be 23.2% while the least percentage obtained from the statement “I laugh about the situation” that is 15% used by nursing students as a transference strategies shown in table 4.2.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-2: Showing Percentage of Transference Coping Strategies used by Nursing Students

S. NO.	Statement	I usually don't do this	I usually do this at a little bit	I usually do this in medium amount	I usually do this at all
Transference					
1	I laugh about the situation.	37%	21%	27%	15%
2	I daydream about things other than this.	21.8%	32%	23%	23.2%
3	I get sympathy and understanding from people.	12.8%	29.5%	27.7%	30%
4	I make fun of the situation.	23.8%	20.5%	29.7%	26%

Emotional Coping Strategies used by Nursing Students

The emotional coping strategies were assessed through six statements mentioned in table 4.3. the highest percentage found 27% from the statement "I get upset" followed by "I say to me "this isn't real." Found to be 25.3%, "I take direct action to

get around the problem" found to be 18%, "I try hard to prevent other things from interfering with my efforts at dealing with this" found to be 17.6% "I try to get emotional support from friends or parents" found to be 14% with the least percentage obtained 12.8% by the statement "I get emotional very fast".

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-3: Showing Percentage of Emotional Coping Strategies used by Nursing Students

S. NO.	Statement	I usually don't do this	I usually do this in medium amount	Little bit I usually do this	I usually do this at all
Getting Emotional					
1	I get emotional very fast.	22%	44%	21.2%	12.8%
2	I say to me "this isn't real."	17.6%	30.3%	26.8%	25.3%
3	I get upset.	20%	25.8%	27.2%	27%
4	I try to get emotional support from friends or parents.	15%	39%	32%	14%
5	I try hard to prevent other things from interfering with my efforts at dealing with this.	11.3%	30.1%	41%	17.6%
6	I take direct action to get around the problem.	29%	31%	22%	18%

Religious Coping Strategies used by Nursing Students

Table 4.4: show the percentages of the statement of religious coping strategies used by nursing students. There were two statements in the questionnaire assessing the religious coping

strategies used by nursing students. From these two statements 33% students marked "I try to find comfort in my religion" with the least percentage obtained 25.5% by the statement "I pray more than usual".

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-4: Showing Percentage of Religious Coping Strategies used by Nursing Students

S. NO.	Statement	I usually don't do this	I usually do this in medium amount	Little bit I usually do this	I usually do this at all
Religious					
1	I pray more than usual.	14.5%	31.5%	28.5%	25.5%
2	I try to find comfort in my religion.	16%	26%	25%	33%

Motivational Coping Strategies used by Nursing Students

Usage of emotional coping strategies were assessed by the six statements mentioned in the table 4.5, the higher percentage obtained 34.8% from the statement “I hold back myself from doing anything too quickly” followed by the statement “I think hard about what steps to take”, “I get used to the idea that it happened” found to be 24.3%, “I give

up the attempt to get what I want” found to be 20%, “I do what has to be done, one step at a time” found to be 13.5%, “I put aside other activities in order to concentrate on this” found to be 11.3%, while the least percentage obtained 10% by the statement “I ask people who have had similar experiences what they did” as a motivational strategies used by nursing students.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-5: Showing Percentage of Motivational Coping Strategies used by Nursing Students

S. NO.	Statement	I usually don't do this	I usually do this in medium amount	Little bit I usually do this	I usually do this at all
Motivation					
1	I hold back myself from doing anything too quickly.	15.5%	25.5%	24.2%	34.8%
2	I get used to the idea that it happened.	24%	28%	28%	20%
3	I give up the attempt to get what I want.	19.8%	39.9%	24.5%	15.8%
4	I make sure not to make matters worse by acting too soon.	16.8%	22.8%	47.4%	13%
5	I ask people who have had similar experiences what they did.	11%	69%	10%	10%
6	I put aside other activities in order to concentrate on this.	38%	27.5%	23.2%	11.3%
7	I think hard about what steps to take.	22%	31.5%	22.2%	24.3%
8	I do what has to be done, one step at a time.	29%	34%	23.5%	13.5%

Negative Coping Strategies used by Nursing Students

As shown in table 4.6 percentages of the statement which is characterized as negative.

The highest percentage was found to be 20% from the statement “I force myself to wait for the right time to do something” followed by “I go to movies or watch TV” found to be 17.3%, with the least

percentage obtained 14.8% by the statement “I get emotional very fast”.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-6: Showing Percentage of Negative Coping Strategies used by Nursing Students

S. NO.	Statement	I usually don't do this	I usually do this in medium amount	Little bit I usually do this	I usually do this at all
Negative Coping					
1	I force myself to wait for the right time to do something.	19%	36%	25%	20%
2	I go to movies or watch TV.	11%	30%	41.7%	17.3%
3	I use medicines to make myself feel better.	49.5%	17.3%	18.4%	14.8%

Problem Solving Coping Strategies used by Nursing Students

As shown in table 4.7 the problem solving strategies usually using by the students were assessed through three statements. Percentages of the statement which is characterized as problem solving, the highest percentage was found to be

38.5% from the statement “I reduce the amount of effort I'm putting into solving the problem” followed by “I think about how I might best handle the problem” found to be 15.8%, with the least percentage obtained 12% by the statement “I take actions to try to get rid of the problem”.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-7: Showing Percentage of Problem Solving Coping Strategies used by Nursing Students

S. NO.	Statement	I usually don't do this	I usually do this at all	Little bit I usually do this	I usually do this in medium amount
Problem Solving					
1	I take actions to try to get rid of the problem.	15.5%	36.3%	36.2%	12%
2	I think about how I might best handle the problem.	30%	29.8%	24.4%	15.8%
3	I reduce the amount of effort I'm putting into solving the problem.	13.5%	23.3%	24.7%	38.5%

Comparison of Different Coping Strategies used by Nursing Students

Table 4.8 shows that which type of coping strategy is commonly using by the nursing students. It was found that religious coping strategies were used mostly by the nursing students in terms of

percentage it was 19.15% whereas, staying optimistic is used by 17.62% participants, problem solving strategies 17.36%, negative strategies 15.53%, transference strategies 11.40%, emotional strategies 11.11% and last but not least motivational strategies were used by 7.83%.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-8: Showing Percentage of Problem-Solving Different Coping Strategies used by Nursing Students

S. NO.	Types of coping strategies	Percentages
1	Motivational	7.83%
2	Emotional	11.11%
3	Transference	11.40%
4	Negative	15.53%
5	Problem solving	17.36%
6	Staying optimistic	17.62%
7	Religious	19.15%

4.0 Discussions

most of the students were female that is 65%. The finding was similar to previous study conducted by Seyed Fatemi⁵⁷. In our study, statement categorized as negative strategies from “I go to movies or watch TV” found to be 17.3%. This result significantly differs from the previous study that evaluated 9% by this statement⁵⁷. Our study also evaluated the use of medicine as a coping mechanism found to be 14%. This result was significantly different from the previous study that evaluated up to 20.5%. The use of alcohols and drugs are more frequent in nursing students of United Kingdom⁵⁸. The result of our study shows 27% from the coping mechanism “I get upset”. This finding was not similar with the study conducted by Seyed Fatemi found to be 18.3%. Another cope mechanism used by nursing student that is “I daydream about things other than this” found to be 23.2% by our study. This finding was not similar to the previous study conducted by Seyed Fatemi⁵⁷ found to be 52.5%. As noted in chapter 4, from the statement “I concentrate my efforts on doing something about it” found to be 17% and this finding was not similar with the study conducted by Seyed Fatemi found to be 50.8%⁵⁷. In addition to this from the statement “I make fun of the situation” found to be 26%. This result was not similar to previous study was conducted in 2007 found to be 37%⁵⁷. While another study was recently conducted by Bamuhair in 2015 found to be 13.1%⁵⁸. This result reveals that with the passage of time, there is trend of decrease of frequency of this coping

strategy. As evaluated by our study from the statement “I try to find comfort in my religion” cope by nursing students found to be 33%. This finding was closely similar to previous study that was conducted recently by Bamuhair in 2015 found to be 36.2%⁶⁹. The finding of our study by the statement of “I think hard about what steps to take” found to be 24.3%. This finding was not exactly but somehow similar to previous studies conducted by Bamuhair in 2015⁵⁸. By nursing students, some coping mechanism are less likely to be used while the other were used more often. UAE and Jordan observed the same results⁵⁹.

5.0 Conclusion

Study shows that the use of coping strategies is on the rise and is increasing day by day. Majority of the students are using positive coping strategies however, some proportion of the nursing students use negative coping strategies as well, which is really a serious issue that needs to be addressed properly. Among coping strategies religious, staying optimistic and problem solving were mostly practiced by nursing students. Our findings also suggest that the most of nursing students are over burdened with their course curriculum. They may improve in terms of study and results etc.

Author Contributions:

Concept and design: SA; Supervision: HBC; Original draft and formal analysis: SA; Data collection: RS; Methodology and literature review: PA Validation and software: RD; Data curation, review, and editing: AN. Ethical Approval: Allied

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